

Studies on mixed ligand complexes involving (*N*-methyliminodiacetic acid)-lead(II) and some bioligands : A voltammetric investigation

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Abstract : Composition and stability constants of mixed ligand complexes of Pb^{II} ion with *N*-methyliminodiacetic acid (MIDA) and some amino acids have been investigated voltammetrically. The reduction of Pb^{II} has been found to be reversible and diffusion controlled involving two electrons in each case. Only MXY₂ type of mixed ligand complexes are formed. The extended method of Schaap and McMasters has been used to evaluate the stability constants of these complexes. By using these stability constants the statistical and electrostatic effects have been discussed.

Keywords : Mixed ligand complexes, voltammetry, *N*-methyliminodiacetic acid (MIDA), amino acids.

Introduction

In continuation of our earlier studies¹, we report here our studies on the mixed ligand complexes of Pb^{II} ion with MIDA and amino acids (DL-threonine, DL-valine, DL-alanine and DL-glycine).

Experimental

All the chemicals (MIDA, DL-isoleucine, L-serine, L-glutamic acid and L-aspartic acid) used as complexing agent were of A.R. grade and their solutions were prepared in double distilled water. The ionic strength was maintained at 0.2 M in all the systems by using KNO₃ as supporting electrolyte. Triton X-100 of 0.001% in the final solution have been used as maxima suppresser. The temperature was maintained constant throughout the investigations at 303 ± 2 K. The experimental techniques were same as described earlier¹.

Results and discussion

Binary systems :

The formation constants of the simple complexes of Pb^{II} with MIDA and Pb^{II} with amino acids (DL-threonine, DL-valine, DL-alanine and DL-glycine) were determined separately by the method of Deford and Hume². The plot of F₀[X] vs [X] has an intercept on F₀[X] axis, equal to unity in all the amino acid systems, called β₀ while the plot of F₁[X] vs [X] gives the value of β₁. In the similar way the plot of F₂[X] vs [X] is a straight line

parallel to [X] axis and is independent to [X] gives the value of β₂. Here β₀, β₁ and β₂ are the stepwise formation/stability constants of complex, which has formed by the addition of 0, 1 and 2 moles of the same ligand to metal ion respectively. This straight line shows that further complexation is not possible. Thus all the amino acids under study, form 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes while MIDA form only 1 : 1 complexes with lead (Fig. 1). The half wave potential of Pb^{II} in 0.2 M KNO₃ was measured accurately and was ranged between -0.388 and -0.391 volt vs SCE.

A single well-defined reduction wave was obtained for each case. The plots of E_{de} vs log I/I_d - I were linear with a slope of 30 ± 2 mV, showing that the two electrons reduction was reversible and diffusion controlled. Stability constants for simple systems are (log β₁, log β₂) : Pb-MIDA (7.33, -), Pb-DL-threonine (4.70, 7.80), Pb-DL-valine (4.50, 7.90), Pb-DL-alanine (5.10, 8.10) and Pb-DL-glycine (5.00, 8.40).

In mixed systems a ligand displacement technique has been used in which a more complexing species is added to a mixture of a metal ion with weaker complexing species. In mixed systems formation of one type of complexes i.e. [Pb(MIDA)(amino acid)₂] has been found. In these systems the concentration of weaker ligand (amino acids) was kept constant at 0.02 M while varying the concentration of strong ligand (MIDA) in each case. A

Fig. 1. Plot of F_{ij} vs MIDA. Pb-MIDA-DL-threonine system; [DL-threonine] = 0.02 M.

shift in half-wave potential to more negative side with increase in amino acid concentration was observed. This shift in half-wave potential is greater in the presence of weaker ligand (amino acids) than in its absence. It signified mixed ligand formation. A single well-defined wave was obtained for each case. The plots of E_{de} vs $\log III_d - I$ were linear with a slope of 30 ± 2 mV, showing that the two electrons reduction was reversible. The direct proportionality of the diffusion current to the mercury column indicates the reduction was entirely diffusion controlled. In all the systems 2.5×10^{-3} M Pb^{II}, 0.2 M KNO₃ and 0.001% Triton X-100 was used. The extended Schaap and McMasters treatment was applied to evaluate the functions F_{00} and F_{10} . These are extended form of Deford and Hume functions F_0 and F_1 respectively. These functions have been deduced using following equations,

$$F_{00} [X, Y] = \text{Anti log} \left(\frac{0.4343 nF}{RT} \Delta E_{1/2} + \log \frac{I_M}{I_C} \right)$$

$$F_{10} = \left[\frac{F_{00} - A}{[X]} \right]$$

Leden's³ graphical extrapolation method has applied on F_{00} and F_{10} respectively to calculate the value of A and B which are intercepts of plots between F_{00} vs [X], and F_{10} vs [X] respectively. The stability constants β_2 were evaluated from the value of B. The values of stability constants for mixed systems are $(\log \beta_{12})$: Pb-MIDA-DL-threonine (16.26); Pb-MIDA-DL-valine (16.31); Pb-MIDA-DL-alanine (16.61); Pb-MIDA-DL-glycine (16.89).

Amino acids form two complexes with Pb while MIDA form only one complex i.e. Pb(MIDA). The values of stability constant for Pb(MIDA) is 7.33 while the values for (Pb-DL-threonine), (Pb-DL-valine), (Pb-DL-alanine) and (Pb-DL-glycine) are 4.70, 4.50, 5.10 and 5.00, respectively. The values of stability constant of Pb-MIDA complexes is much higher than the values of the Pb-amino acids complexes, hence only one mixed complex i.e. $[Pb(MIDA)(\text{amino acid})_2]$ is formed. The tendency to add

Y to Pb[Y] and Y₂ to Pb[X] can be compared. The log K values are (3.10, 8.93), (3.40, 8.98), (3.00, 9.28) and (3.40, 9.56) for all the systems respectively. In this case because 1 : 1 complex i.e. [Pb(MIDA)(amino acid)] is not forming we compare the addition of Y₂ over Pb[X] instead of Y to Pb[X]. The log K values indicate that the formation of Pb[XY₂] is favored by the addition of opposite ligand in all the systems.

The tendency to form mixed ligand complexes in solution can be expressed quantitatively by other approach compares the difference in stability ($\Delta \log K$), which is the result from the subtraction of two constants and must therefore, be a constant. This corresponds to :

$$\Delta \log K = \log K_{MAB}^{MA} - \log K_{MB}^M$$

Since more coordination positions are available for bonding of the first ligand [A] to a given multivalent metal ion than for the second ligand [B].

$$\log K_{MA}^M > \log K_{MA_2}^{MA}$$

Usually one expects to observe negative values for $\Delta \log K$. Another probably more satisfactory manner is to determine the statistical values for $\Delta \log K$. The statistical values for regular octahedron is 5/12 and $\Delta \log K_{oh} = -0.4$. For a square planer (sp), the value of $\Delta \log K_{sp} = -0.6$ and for the distorted octahedron (do), the statistical values i.e. $\Delta \log K_{do} =$ lie between -0.9 to -0.3 .

The $\Delta \log K$ values can be obtained using the follow-

ing equations :

$$\Delta \log K_{12} = \log \beta_{12} - (\log \beta_{10} + \log \beta_{02})$$

The observed values of $\Delta \log K_{12}$ are (+1.13, +1.08, +1.18, +1.16), for Pb-MIDA-DL-threonine, Pb-MIDA-DL-valine, Pb-MIDA-DL-alanine and Pb-MIDA-DL-glycine systems respectively.

The $\Delta \log K$ values are higher than statistical value, which again proves that the ternary complexes are more stable than expected from statistical reasons.

Conclusion :

From the above investigations it is found that Pb form only one type of ternary stable complex with MIDA [X] and amino acids [Y] i.e. MX_2Y .

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